

SELF-EFFICACY AND EMOTIONAL STABILITY OF TEACHERS ON SELF-SATISFACTION: DIRECTION TOWARDS A PROPOSED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Self-efficacy of teachers may influence how individuals will approach tasks, responsibilities and challenges in the workplace. Self- efficacy and emotional stability of teachers can be determining factors of self-satisfaction in the profession. The study dealt on the relationship of self-efficacy and emotional stability on self-satisfaction in terms of outcome expectations, career commitment, resiliency to adversity, self-awareness, self-professional development and teaching effectiveness. Moreover, self-efficacy and emotional stability were also investigated in terms of personal and professional satisfaction of public- school teachers in the workplace. Researcher-made questionnaire surveys were conducted among one hundred fifty-six (156) elementary school teachers for school year 2020-2021 who are employed in seven (7) schools at DepEd Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon. The researcher employed descriptive- correlational method. Teachers understand the possible effects of their actions and deals better to challenging tasks in this time of pandemic to attain better performances in their school duties. The study revealed that there are significant relationships of self-efficacy and emotional stability with that of teacher's self-satisfaction. Moreover, it indicates that self-efficacy indicated by their outcome, career, and resiliency are correlated with their self-satisfaction. Teachers, as one of the sources of learning should not only focus on the subject matter but they may also focus on their career path progression to improve their self- professional development. Furthermore, teachers may engage in conducting action researches to strengthened their career productivity and opportunity. The school heads may provide self-professional development plan such as Faculty Development Session to provide support to teachers on improving their self-efficacy and emotional stability.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Emotional Stability, Self-Satisfaction